

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Testing Polymer Melts Using the TLS-HT300 Needle Probe

The following Application Highlight features the use of the Transient Line Source (TLS) method in the thermal conductivity testing of polymer at elevated temperatures.

In recent years, the manufacturing landscape has been reshaped by the rise of additive manufacturing (also known as 3D printing) as well as advanced injection moulding processes. These types of materials are frequently used in industries such as aerospace, healthcare, and electronics due to their strength, flexibility, and lightweight nature. However, when applying these products in sensitive areas, it is important that the polymer melts used are fully characterized, both for end use, and the thermal processing that is involved.

Figure 1. Left) 3D printing system. Right) Trident system with TLS sensor.

While commonly used polymers such as acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and polyethylene (PE) are well characterized at room temperature, reliable high-temperature data is not as abundant. Since many of the engineering polymers used in these areas tend to have a melting point well above 100°C, it is necessary to characterize their properties under representative conditions as thermal conductivity is subject to the temperature range of interest.

Figure 2. Schematic describing the insertion process into the melt.

C-Therm's High-Temperature Transient Line Source (TLS-HT300) is sheathed in stainless steel, enabling it to measure challenging, viscous materials, including polymer melts safely and reliably. The following data represents the testing of ABS and polystyrene (PS) from room temperature to the max temperature of reference data available (200°C and 280°C, respectively).

High-Temperature Polymer Testing Results

Figure 3. Thermal conductivity data of ABS up to 200°C (left) and PS up to 280°C (right).

Compared to the available reference data, thermal conductivity results across the measured temperature range are within 10% of the expected values for both ABS and PS. It should be noted that the ABS did not reach a fully melted state during this testing. While reliable reference data above the temperatures listed is not available, the TLS-HT300 can test up to 300°C. A measurement of PS was conducted at 300°C and compared to the available reference data. Although there is no reference value to compare, this value does follow the expected trend (within 10%).

Figure 4. Comparison between the measured 300C data and the available reference data.

The influence of temperature is a critical consideration for these types of applications as it has a direct bearing on the processing conditions and the quality of the produced parts. While not discussed herein, another important factor to consider in these applications is the impact of pressure. During the extrusion and/or moulding process, the melt is often under high-pressure conditions which also impacts the overall process. C-Therm's TLS-HT300 allows for testing under both temperature and pressurized conditions to allow for a truly representative understanding of material performance.

Figure 5. Trident system with TLS sensor and high-pressure cell.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com